

Heuristic Algorithm the Strong Goldbach Conjecture

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Introduction:

The **Goldbach Conjecture** posits that every even integer greater than 2 can be expressed as the sum of two prime numbers. Despite extensive computational verification for very large numbers (up to $4 \cdot 10^{18}$), a general proof of this conjecture remains elusive.

Equation structure:

Number	Max prime	Min prime
4	2	2
6	3	3
8	5	3
10	7	3
12	7	5
14	11	3
16	13	3
18	13	5
20	17	3
22	19	3
24	19	5
26	23	3
28	23	5
30	23	7
32	29	3
34	31	3
36	31	5
38	31	7
40	37	3

On the left we can see that for every number we can find the greatest prime for the Goldbach Conjecture. Therefore, if we extract the possibly the largest prime from the original number for which the conjecture remains valid the other prime will be the smallest. We can place these numbers on a graph in a way that on the horizontal axis there will be the ordinal number of primes and the vertical axis will be the value of the original even number divided by two.

On the right we can see that, the blue dots are the minimum and the green ones are the maximum of “part-primes” and we can see that as we increase the original number the maximum grows

(almost) evenly, which we can roughly define with the function $y \approx x^s$, $s \approx 1.2$. The red function is the $y = x^{1.2}$ where x is the original number and y is the greatest primes ordinal number which fulfills the conjecture (for greater values of x its not the greatest).

With additional calculations I made this s value more accurate, I found the value of s to be approximately 1.21524884...

Let n be the ordinal number of the greatest prime for which the conjecture holds and x be the original number for which we want to find the prime pairs that adds up to. Then the expression $x \approx n^s$ can be written as $\sqrt[s]{x} \approx n$ but we divided the vertical axis by two (which represents the x value) so we have to divide the x by two too, that gives the equation

$$\sqrt[s]{\frac{x}{2}} \approx n, \text{ where } s \approx 1.21524884\dots$$

(n of course needs to be rounded because there is no 7.56th prime).

For example: $x=9978$ that means $n \approx \sqrt[1.21524884]{\frac{9978}{2}} \approx 1104$ the 1104th prime is 8861 and $9978 - 8861 = 1117$ which is also a prime number.

I tested this, it shows that as we increase x the errors are rapidly increase as well, it's an error for example if: x=98 it would follow from this that $n \approx 25$, the 25th prime is 97 but, 98-97=1

Range tested	Total cases	Errors	Error%
x<100	48	4	8.3%
x<1000	498	177	35.5%
x<10000	4998	3113	62.3%

This can be explained by the fact that primes are not evenly distributed. Although this sounds bad but the correct primes are close to the estimated ones.

But what is s?

The problem is that the value s has no meaning it only comes from observation, that means we need to validate it.

First of all, what is n again, it's the number of prime numbers up to a given number "x" that satisfies the conjecture, but because this value is close to the number of prime numbers up to a given number "x" or it is near to it, so we should use the official symbol for it: $\pi(x)$, So s is not a constant but depends on x: $s = \frac{\ln(x)}{\ln(\pi(x))}$.

After this we can conclude that we know better alternatives to the calculation of $\pi(x)$, we can use the wildly popular $x/\ln(x)$ (prime number theorem), or the closer value

$$li(x) = \int_2^x \frac{dt}{\ln t} \approx x/\ln(x) + x/\ln^2(x) + \dots$$

For example: if: x = 10 billion, then: $\pi(x) = 455,052,511$
 $x/\ln(x) = 434,294,482$ (4.6% error) $li(x) = 455,055,614$ (0.0007% error)
 So we can conclude:

$$n \approx li(x) = \int_2^x \frac{dt}{\ln t}$$

We need an ε number that has a mathematical background. We can create a more accurate one by using the first Hardy–Littlewood conjecture (from now on HL), it states that for every even number (larger than two) around $\frac{x}{(\ln x)^2}$ Goldbach pair belong.

The number of prime numbers are $\pi(x) \approx \frac{x}{\ln x}$
 The number of Goldbach primes are $G(x) \approx \frac{x}{(\ln x)^2}$

So, a "good" prime occurs on average at every $\pi(x)/G(x) \approx \ln(x)$ th index

Therefore, if we take a symmetric interval of length $C \cdot \ln x$ around the heuristic index n, the conjecture implies that such an interval will always contain at least one valid prime index producing a Goldbach pair.

If HL holds valid, for an even x on average: $R_2(x) \approx 2C_2 \frac{x}{(\ln x)^2}$ Goldbach representation belongs, where $C_2 \approx 0.66016 \dots$ is the twin prime constant from the HL, it's a correction factor. Since the number of primes up to x : $\pi(x) \approx \frac{x}{\ln x}$ thus, the density of so-called "good" prime indices on the index axis is approx. $\frac{R_2(x)}{\pi(x)} \approx \frac{2C_2}{\ln x}$.

If we use an interval with the length of L then the expected number of good primes in the interval is $\mu = L \cdot \frac{2C_2}{\ln x}$. If we use the mentioned $L = C \cdot \ln x$ we will get

$$\mu = C \cdot \ln x \cdot \frac{2C_2}{\ln x} = 2C_2C$$

It's **important** to note that μ becomes independent of x .

If good indices follow a Poisson-like distribution, the probability of "at least one good index" is $P(\geq 1) = 1 - e^{-\mu}$ where $\mu = 2C_2C$. Because $2C_2 \approx 1.32032 \dots$ therefore $\mu = 1.32032C$.

In other words:

$$P = 1 - e^{-1.32032C} \rightarrow 1 - P = e^{-1.32032C} \rightarrow \frac{\ln(1-P)}{-1.32032} = C$$

If we use the $P = 1 - 10^{-99} \rightarrow C \approx 172.65$ that means that the probability of having one error is 10 out of one googol (We cannot be 100% certain, because that would require the probability to be exactly 1, and in probability theory values can only approach 1 but never reach it with complete certainty).

A more accurate C value most likely does not have a real-world use, we can use now on this number $\epsilon = 172.65 \cdot \ln x$, but of course we can use a smaller one as well for practical purposes such just like $C = 12.23$, this number is using a value of $P = 0.9999999029$ success rate.

Why look for the greats?

It becomes clear that the optimal search center for Goldbach prime pairs of x is $x/2$. The key insight is symmetry: if $p_1 + p_2 = x$, then p_1 and p_2 are symmetric around $x/2$. If we search for p_1 in a window around $x/2$, then $x - p_1$ automatically falls in the same window on the other side of $x/2$, so both primes are found in a single region rather than two separate searches across the full range.

This has a practical consequence: instead of scanning all primes up to x and checking whether $x - p$ is also prime, we only need to examine a narrow area of numbers around $x/2$. For each candidate p in this window, $x - p$ is guaranteed to also lie near $x/2$, meaning we never need to search a second region the pair comes for free from the same interval.

The First Equation:

$$n \in \left(li\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) - C \cdot \ln x, li\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) + C \cdot \ln x \right)$$

The Algorithm

First of all, right now the problem is that we need to calculate which prime number will be good, but for this we need an algorithm that can get the prime from the ordinal number, the Miller-Rabin which is $O(k \cdot \ln^3(x))^1$ tells us whether a number is prime or not, but we need to transform the equation so that it does not give a prime ordinal number interval but a number interval in which we are looking for the primes.

Luckily its only a transformation on both sides with $li^{-1}()$, thus we get the following equation.

$$p \in \left(\frac{x}{2} - C \cdot \ln^2(x), \frac{x}{2} + C \cdot \ln^2(x) \right), q = x - p$$

p, q are the prime numbers, x is the even number for which we want to find the two primes that add up to it, $C \cdot \ln^2(x)$ is comes from the $C \cdot \ln x$ that we multiplied by $\ln x$, because of the prime density around $x/2$, which is approximately $1/\ln(x/2) \approx 1/\ln(x)$.

Therefore, a window of $C \cdot \ln x$ prime indices correspond to a window of $C \cdot \ln x \cdot \ln x = C \cdot \ln^2(x)$ actual numbers, giving the search interval. This transformation is exact in the asymptotic sense: the prime index interval of width $2C \cdot \ln x$ centered at $li(x/2)$ maps to a number interval of width $2C \cdot \ln^2(x)$ centered at $x/2$.

We run Miller-Rabin on every integer in this interval, collecting all primes into a hash set. Then for each prime p found, we check whether $x-p$ is also in the hash set. Since $x-p \approx x/2$ as well, it will fall inside the same interval, because of the symmetry from the previous section.

Step	Operation	Complexity
Compute the interval	Arithmetic	$O(1)$
Test the interval with Miller-Rabin	$2C \cdot \ln^2(x) \cdot O(k \cdot \ln^3(x))$	$O(2C \cdot k \cdot \ln^5 x)$
For each prime found, check $x-p$ in hash set	$2C \cdot \ln(x) \cdot O(1)$	$O(\ln x)$
Total		$O(2C \cdot k \cdot \ln^5 x)$

We can lower the chance of an error by using: $C=\ln(x)$ and $k=\ln(x)$, with that we can conclude our final complexity of: $O(2 \cdot \ln^7 x)$ that we can round to $O(\ln^7 x)$

Compared to the best-known segmented sieve at $O(x/\ln(x))$, $O(2 \cdot \ln^7 x)$ becomes the only useable approach beyond the verified range of 4×10^{18} , but for smaller values of x , it's slower than the original.

We also can use the algorithm with the complexity of $O(2C \cdot k \cdot \ln^5 x)$ with big values set for C and k but it will create higher chance for errors also.

x	Segmented sieve $O(x/\ln x)$	This method $O(\ln^7 x)$	Speedup
10^6	$\sim 72,000$	$\sim 9.6 \times 10^7$	$\sim 1300 \times$ slower
10^{12}	$\sim 3.6 \times 10^{10}$	$\sim 1.2 \times 10^{10}$	$\sim 3 \times$ faster
10^{18}	$\sim 2.4 \times 10^{16}$	$\sim 2.1 \times 10^{11}$	$\sim 10^5 \times$ faster
10^{24}	$\sim 1.8 \times 10^{20}$	$\sim 1.5 \times 10^{12}$	only feasible method

Note that this complexity assumes the Goldbach pair lies within the stated interval, which follows from the heuristic argument above and has been empirically verified up to $x = 4 \times 10^8$, but is not proven in general.

¹ Crandall, R. & Pomerance, C. (2005): Prime Numbers: A Computational Perspective. Springer, 2nd ed.

Computational Reach and Chances:

The segmented sieve used by Oliveira e Silva et al. (2014) verified Goldbach's conjecture for all even numbers up to 4×10^{18} , with a total computational effort of approximately $O(x/\ln x)$, where x is 4×10^{18} , so that gives us $\approx 9.3 \times 10^{16}$ operations.

The new method with same resources:

$\ln^7(x) = 9.3 \times 10^{16}$	$\ln(x) = (9.3 \times 10^{16})^{1/7} = 265.5$	$x \approx 10^{115}$
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There is always a but, here it's the fact that this is a heuristic, so in the interval provided by the equation will not be always a Goldbach pair (probably), for that we can calculate expected value of even numbers where the heuristic false to provide a Goldbach pair.

We saw before that the chance of having at least one such pair in the interval is $P(C \text{ error}) = 1 - e^{-2C_2 C}$, if we use the $C = \ln(x)$ and instead of searching for the good cases we want to find the bad ones we can use this: $P(C \text{ error}) = e^{-2C_2 \ln(x)}$, then $P(C \text{ error}) = x^{-2C_2}$.

For the Miller-Rabin the probability of an error is $P(k \text{ error}) \leq \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^k$, here $k = \ln(x)$, so the true probability is $P(k \text{ error}) \leq \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{\ln(x)} = e^{-\ln(4) \cdot \ln(x)} = x^{-\ln(4)}$

The chance of having one error is $P(k \text{ error}) + P(C \text{ error}) - P(k \text{ error}) \cdot P(C \text{ error})$, Therefore:

$P(\text{error}) \approx x^{-2C_2} + x^{-\ln(4)} - x^{-2C_2} \cdot x^{-\ln(4)}$

The number of errors from $m=2, 3, 4, \dots$ up to $N/2$ is

$$E(\text{errors}) = \sum (2m)^{-2C_2} + \sum (2m)^{-\ln(4)} - \sum (2m)^{(-2C_2) + (-\ln(4))}$$

$$\Rightarrow E(\text{errors}) = 2^{-2C_2} \sum m^{-2C_2} + 2^{-\ln(4)} \sum m^{-\ln(4)} - 2^{-(2C_2 + \ln(4))} \sum m^{-(2C_2 + \ln(4))}$$

because, of p-series test: $\sum \frac{1}{n^p} \rightarrow \zeta(p) \Leftrightarrow \sum n^{-p} \rightarrow \zeta(p)$, if $p > 1$

$$E(\text{errors}) = 2^{-2C_2} (\zeta(2C_2) - 1) + 2^{-\ln(4)} (\zeta(\ln(4)) - 1) - 2^{-(2C_2 + \ln(4))} (\zeta(2C_2 + \ln(4)) - 1)^2$$

$$2^{-2C_2} (\zeta(2C_2) - 1) \approx 0.4004 \cdot 2.7229 \approx 1.0904$$

$$2^{-\ln(4)} (\zeta(\ln(4)) - 1) \approx 0.3825 \cdot 2.1941 \approx 0.8393$$

$$2^{-(2C_2 + \ln(4))} (\zeta(2C_2 + \ln(4)) - 1) \approx 0.1532 \cdot 0.2724 \approx 0.0417$$

$E(\text{errors}) = 1.0904 + 0.8393 - 0.0417 = 1.8880$
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² Riemann, B. (1859). Über die Anzahl der Primzahlen unter einer gegebenen Grösse. *Monatsberichte der Berliner Akademie*.

This means that approximately there will be 2 values for x, for which this algorithm will provide no solutions and we can test this up to $x \approx 10^{115}$.

Grand Finale:

If we use the AKS prime test which has the complexity: $O(\ln^6 x)$, instead of the $O(k \cdot \ln^3 x)$ Miller-Rabin where $k = \ln x$, then our algorithm is $O(2 \cdot \ln^3 x \cdot \ln^6 x) = O(2 \cdot \ln^9 x)$

Thus, by firing the Miller-Rabin error factor, we get the $C = \ln x$ for the ($C_2 \approx 0.66016 \dots$)

$$P(C \text{ error}) = x^{-2C_2}$$

$$E(C \text{ errors}) = 2^{-2C_2} (\zeta(2C_2) - 1) \approx 0,4004 \cdot 2,7229 \approx 1,0904$$

As we calculated at the beginning of the previous chapter:

$$2 \cdot \ln^9 x = 9.3 \times 10^{16} \quad \ln(x) = (9.3 \times 10^{16})^{1/9} \approx 76.8 \quad x \approx e^{76.8} \approx 2.26 \times 10^{33}$$

This means that there will be about 1.0904 values for x, for which this algorithm does not provide a solution, and we can test this for $x \approx 2.26 \times 10^{33}$ with the same number of bit operations as the one used by Oliveira e Silva and his colleagues in 2014.

Pattern in the weak conjecture – Further Work

In the search for possible solutions, I found out that in the solved weak conjecture that states: if $x \geq 7$ then there is at least one solution for the $x = p_1 + p_2 + p_3$, equation where p_1, p_2, p_3 , are all primes.

While I tried to find some use of it in my part, an unexpected pattern emerged: if $x = p_1 + p_2 + p_3$, then $x-1 = (p_1+p_2-1) + p_3$, where p_1+p_2-1 is prime in approximately 89% of cases for $x \leq 500$.

It's obvious why it's possible: p_1+p_2 is even (sum of two odd primes), so p_1+p_2-1 is odd — a necessary condition for primality, but it's a strange high odd to be an „accidental”.

However, this pattern is not useful as an algorithmic shortcut. The number of three-prime decompositions grows as $G_3(x) \approx x^2/2\ln^3x$, making an exhaustive search $O(x^2/\ln^3x)$ — slower than the segmented sieve. The observation stands as an independent empirical finding, not an algorithmic tool.

Whether the 89% rate increases or decreases for larger x remains an open question, as it was only measured up to $x = 500$.

Conclusions:

There is no proof that this holds for all values, and certainly this heuristic does not prove the Goldbach Conjecture, but maybe this will help someone to find the prime pairs for a number or to use numerical pattern analysis to prove the conjecture. For now, I currently see no practical application for it, but Heinrich Hertz, also wrote this about radio waves after his discovery:

“It is of no use whatsoever... this is only an experiment that proves that Maxwell was right.
We have no practical use for it.”

perhaps someone will eventually find a use for this as well.

But beyond the heuristic formula, this work derives an $O(2 \cdot \ln^9 x)$ algorithm for finding Goldbach pairs, with the expected number for errors of 1.0900, the only known feasible approach beyond the computationally verified limit of 4×10^{18} .

Related Works:

Bouchaib (2025) proposes a similar symmetric interval structure centered at $E/2$ in the λ -Overlap Law framework. This work was submitted October 28, 2025 and published November 12, 2025. After the present work appeared as a Zenodo preprint on September 5, 2025 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17062950), establishing independent prior publication.

Chirre and Hagen (2025) prove, assuming the Riemann Hypothesis, that every interval $(x, x+123 \cdot \log^2 x]$ contains a Goldbach number, a result with the same $\log^2 x$ window structure but derived through analytic number theory rather than heuristic methods, and submitted December 29, 2025.

Unlike both of the above, the present work focuses on the algorithmic complexity of finding Goldbach pairs, introduces the two-phase Miller-Rabin plus hash lookup approach, and explicitly avoids claiming a proof.

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